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Perspective of Prospective Teacher's on Classroom Assignment

Dr. Gautam G. Gaude

Assistant Professor, GVM'S Dr. Dada Vaidya College of Education, Farmagudi, Ponda, Goa, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Gautam G. Gaude

Abstract

The perspective of prospective teachers was found out through self-constructed questionnaire. The questionnaire was administered on First year B.Ed. prospective teachers of GVM'S Dr. Dada Vaidya College of Education, Farmagudi, Ponda Goa for academic year 2024-25. A total of 61 participants completed the questionnaire. Initially, the prospective teachers reviewed the literature from the "daily digest" on the cyber crime portal. They also prepared an educational talk based on the file titled "Cyber Hygiene For Cyber Space" from the cyber crime portal, which was presented to school students in Goa during their one-month internship program. Prospective teachers were instructed to take any one subtopic from the above mention file and deliver one talk in a classroom. After the internship concluded, data was collected from the prospective teachers. It was found that there is a recognized necessity to inform students about online safety, responsible use of the internet, and the dangers associated with cyber threats. Additionally, it was suggested that future perspective teachers should be made aware of the rising incidence of cybercrime through appropriate training.

Keywords: Prospective teacher, perspective, cyber crime, classroom assignment

Introduction

"The word education is derived from the Latin word 'educare' meaning 'to raise' and 'to bring up' (NCERT, 2014)" [6]. Educational growth is essential for the overall development of an individual. It helps one understand the concepts of right and wrong, good and bad, ethical and unethical, and so on. Proper educational guidance enables individuals to make appropriate decisions in their lives. Teachers are key resources in guiding learners towards success. Teacher education programs prepare prospective teachers to enhance their teaching and learning processes, ultimately helping them to become successful teachers in the future.

In the teacher education program, prospective teachers study various subjects, including foundations of education, learning resources, action research, teaching approaches and strategies, learner and learning, guidance and counseling, inclusive education, environmental education, fine arts, and performing arts. The curriculum also includes the methodologies for subjects such as Mathematics, Science, English, Marathi, Hindi, Konkani, Geography, and History. Each subject has a designated percentage of internal marks,

allowing teacher educators to assign topics for projects, assignments, and other activities. As part of the "Learning Resources" subject, the prospective teachers at GVM's Dr. Dada Vaidya College of Education in Farmagudi, Ponda, Goa, were assigned an assignment during their school internship program. They were instructed to conduct a literature review based on the "Daily Digest" from the cyber crime portal. Additionally, the students were tasked with organizing an awareness program at a school, choosing one topic from the file titled "Cyber Hygiene for Cyber Space," which was available on the cyber crime portal.

Cybercrimes are illegal activities that can target individuals, businesses, or organizations through the use of computers, the internet, or mobile devices. "For enabling students to understand cybersecurity the prospective teachers should have its understanding so that they can pass them to the future generations (Shikha D. *et al.*, 2023) [7]". "As teachers shape our youth's future, it is proposed that government and institutions educate Teacher Trainees about cybercrime (Kumar *et al.*, 2021) [3]". "Creation of Cyber Crime awareness among the B.Ed. Pupil Teachers will help in the creation of cyber crime awareness among the students as

these Pupil Teachers are preparing to enter the teaching profession (Bansal, 2017) [1]”. This assignment on cybercrime was designed to highlight the seriousness of the growing threat posed by cyber crime. In this assignment, prospective teachers first examine various cases of cyber crime reported on a cybercrime portal. Next, they select a topic from the file titled "Cyber Hygiene for Cyberspace" and deliver a talk at the school where they were completing their one-month internship as first-year B.Ed. students. The purpose of the talk was to make school students aware of the increasing threat of cybercrime.

Review of related literature

In 2023, Deep Shikha 2023 [7] *et al.* examined awareness level of preservice teachers regarding cybercrime and cybersecurity. The research sample included 69 preservice teachers from teacher education programs specifically the Central University of Jammu and the University of Jammu, through a simple random sampling method. Data was collected through a Self-Constructed Cybercrime Awareness Questionnaire. The study's results indicated that most respondents have a moderate awareness of cyber crime issues, with only a small number demonstrating a high level of awareness.

Kumar *et al.* (2021) [3] examined the awareness of cyber crime among teacher trainees. Data was gathered through a random sampling method, by selecting 200 B.Ed. students from education colleges in Ludhiana. This sample included 50 males and 150 females, as well as an equal distribution of 100 students from rural areas and 100 from urban areas. The researcher created a unique scale to measure cyber crime awareness. The results indicated that male teacher trainees exhibited higher awareness levels compared to female teacher trainees, also urban teacher trainees demonstrated greater awareness than their rural counterparts, suggesting that female and rural teacher trainees require additional support.

Bansal (2017) [1] conducted a study comparing the level of cyber crime awareness among teachers from science and social science backgrounds. The research utilized the Cyber Crime Awareness Scale developed by Rajasekar (2011) [8]. A sample of 50 B.Ed. students was chosen for the study. The findings indicate that B.Ed. pupil Science teachers demonstrate a significantly higher level of awareness than B.Ed. pupil Social studies teachers. Therefore, it is recommended that teacher evaluators and policymakers foster environments that enhance awareness among Social studies pupil teachers

Objectives of the study

1. To understand the usefulness of review of daily digest assignment.
2. To understand the awareness of prospective teachers regarding cyber crime portal daily digest uploads.
3. To understand the opinion of prospective teachers regarding training school students on cyber crime.
4. To understand the challenges that were faced by prospective teachers while conducting awareness talk on cyber crime in school.
5. To understand the opinion of prospective teachers regarding providing training to prospective teachers on cyber crime.

6. To understand the interest of prospective teachers in conducting cyber crime awareness sessions during in-service.
7. To understand opinion of prospective teachers on increasing rate of cyber crimes.

Methodology of the study

The researcher employed a descriptive survey method to collect data from prospective teachers at GVM's Dr. Dada Vaidya College of Education in Farmagudi, Ponda, Goa. Initially, an in-depth study was conducted with a few first-year B.Ed. students. Based on feedback from the interviews, the researcher modified the prepared questions to better meet the study's needs. The questionnaire was developed in two stages. First, the investigator prepared the initial set of questions. Then, through interviews with approximately 10 students, the investigator assessed the relevance of these questions. This process led to the deletion, modification, and addition of several questions. After finalizing the questionnaire, it was distributed to students via a Google Form link. A total of 61 prospective teachers completed the form.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Objective 01: To understand the usefulness of review of daily digest assignment.

Fig 1: Is review was useful in Learning?

Fig 2: How it was useful in Learning?

From Figure 1, it is observed that 94% of prospective teachers believe that the assignment on reviewing the daily digest was useful for their learning, while 6% indicated that it might be somewhat useful. In Figure 2, it is noted that 86% of prospective teachers stated that the assignment helped them understand the various types of crimes, how cyber crimes occur, and what safety measures can be taken to prevent cyber crimes.

Objective 02: To understand the awareness of prospective teachers regarding cyber crime portal daily digest uploads.

Fig 3: Awareness about Daily Digest upload

Fig 4: Have you visited cyber crime portal anytime?

Figure 3 shows that 71% of prospective teachers were unaware of the daily digest uploads on the cybercrime portal, while 26% were aware of it. Figure 4 indicates that 78% of prospective teachers have not visited the cybercrime portal, whereas only 22% have visited it.

Objective 03: To understand the opinion of prospective teachers regarding training school teachers on cyber crime.

Fig 5: Need to train school students

Fig 6: For which grade talk was conducted?

Figure 5 indicates that 100% of prospective teachers believe there is a need to train school-going students on cyber crime. Figure 6 shows that 36% of prospective teachers delivered educational talks to students in the eighth grade, while 32% did so for seventh-grade students. However, very few delivered talks to students in other grades

Objective 04: To understand the challenges that were faced by prospective teachers while conducting awareness talk on cyber crime in school.

Since open questions were posed to prospective teachers, the responses were explained in descriptive forms. It was found that the majority of students faced difficulties in conveying complex technical information in a simple manner. Additionally, discussing sensitive topics such as phishing and sexual harassment proved to be challenging. The challenges included keeping students engaged with technical subjects, addressing their misunderstandings about online safety, and raising awareness of risks without instilling fear

Objective 05: To understand the opinion of prospective teachers regarding training to prospective teachers of educational colleges on cyber crime.

Objective 06: To understand the interest of prospective teachers in conducting cyber crimes awareness sessions during their future in-service.

Fig 7: Prospective teacher need training

Fig 8: Interested in conducting more session

From Figure 07, it can be interpreted that 93% of prospective teachers suggested providing training on cyber crime to students at educational colleges. Meanwhile, Figure 08 shows that 85% of prospective teachers expressed interest in conducting more cyber crime sessions in schools once they are employed.

Objective 07: To understand opinion of prospective teachers on cyber crimes

The following are the opinions of prospective teachers regarding cyber crimes

- All students should be made aware of the different types of cyber crimes and the precautionary measures to take while using digital resources.
- They must also be instructed on whom to approach and how to seek help when they encounter trouble. Cyber crime awareness programs should be implemented for everyone, from young children to older adults, as anyone can become a target of these crimes.
- As technology advances, cyber crime is increasing at an alarming rate. However, with proper guidance and awareness of safe technology practices, these problems can be effectively managed. As teachers, we have the opportunity to significantly reduce cyber crime through awareness, given our close relationship with students.

Conclusions and suggestions

- It can be concluded that the classroom assignment focused on reviewing the daily digest from the cybercrime portal was very beneficial for prospective teachers. Such assignments should be introduced in colleges to raise student awareness about the increasing prevalence of cybercrime.
- Despite the existing efforts to create awareness about cybercrime, it seems we are still failing to promote the initiatives of the cybercrime portal effectively. The Government of India has made significant strides in this regard by providing online resources on their website. Schools and colleges need to enhance awareness about safety measures to prevent cybercrime.
- The feedback provided by prospective teachers highlights the necessity of training school students, which is crucial, especially after the delivery of an educational talk. By guiding students on safe internet practices, we can help them embrace technology while avoiding its potential dangers. Cybercrime awareness should be included in the curriculum starting from the elementary school level, and regular informational talks should be conducted.
- From the opinions expressed by prospective teachers, it is clear that there is a need for appropriate training for them. This training will equip them with the knowledge of various types of cyber fraud, enabling them to effectively educate school-going students about these issues.

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